

Effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy and Conventional Method of Teaching Mathematics on Students' Achievement in Graph Plotting

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Abstract

The study engaged the quasi-experimental descriptive survey approach to investigate the effect of cooperative learning strategy and conventional methods of teaching mathematics on students' achievement in graph plotting within the Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The study engaged 70 students from two intact classes of Senior Secondary School two students of Obinomba Mixed Secondary School, Obinomba. The two intact classes were used to represent the experimental and control groups, with the experimental group being taught graph plotting using a cooperative learning strategy and the control group was taught using the conventional method of teaching mathematics. The study lasted for five weeks, and a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. The Mathematics Achievement Test on Graph Plotting (MATGP) was used to assess students' achievement in graph plotting for the groups after they received instructional intervention. A reliability of 0.8 was yielded for the instrument using Richard Kuderson-21. The data obtained from the instrument was analyzed using a t-test of independence at $p \leq 0.05$ significance level. The result showed that students in the experimental group performed better than those in the control group. The study thus bridges a knowledge gap that informs the improvement of the methodology engaged in teaching senior secondary school mathematics and promotes science education in secondary schools. The study recommended integrating a cooperative learning strategy in teaching graph plotting in Delta State Secondary Schools, Nigeria.

Keywords: *Graph Plotting, Conventional Instruction Method, Cooperative Learning Strategy, Science Education, Students' Achievement.*

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Introduction

Graph plotting is very important concept in Nigerian science education at the secondary school level, as it helps learners acquire scientific knowledge and critical thinking skills that are essential for building their foundation in data analysis and interpretation. However, various teaching methods can enhance the learning experiences in this area, but teachers often use the conventional teacher-centered method in the pedagogy of graph plotting in mathematics and physics classes (Iroriteraye-Adjekpovu & Nwabuaku, 2024). The interest in graph plotting arose from the observed poor academic achievement of Nigerian science students as reported by the WAEC chief examiners report in 2019, 2020, and 2022, besides the need to improve students' achievement in the area. This corroborates the work of Ejiwale (2013) who

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observed rightly, that the problem of poor performance and participation in STEM is more serious in developing countries. To advance science education generally, strategies targeted at improving standard instructional experiences must be deliberated and reflected upon as students' achievement in a subject is closely related to the quality of their learning experiences in that subject area (Nwabuaku, 2022).

Lessani, Yunus & Bakar (2017) specified that the conventional method of teaching mathematics involves a teacher-centered style, with giving lectures being the prevailing situation. However, the cooperative learning strategy has proven to be an effective educational strategy in which small groups of students with diverse abilities harmoniously utilize a range of learning activities and meaningful interaction, to enhance their educational capabilities (Nnorom, 2015; Arra, Antonio, & Antonio, 2011).

Ajaja and Eravwoke (2010) examined the impact of the cooperative learning strategy on students' performance. They concluded that students generally achieve significantly higher test scores when taught using the cooperative learning strategy compared to traditional classroom settings. Similarly, Felder and Brent (2007) observed that a cooperative learning strategy is effective in stimulating metacognitive thought, diligence, and intrinsic motivation among students. Research has shown that to excel in difficult mathematics concepts like graph plotting, students should have the chance to establish active interactions, where they can communicate and reason mathematically while developing self-confidence in problem-solving (Chen et al., 2021; Nnorom, 2015, Altun 2015; Shimazoe & Aldrich 2010; Zakaria, Chin & Daud, 2010, and Khan & Akhtar, 2017). This study is therefore a response to the knowledge gap aiming to establish the impact of cooperative learning strategy and conventional teaching methods on how students' achieve in graph plotting, in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State.

Research Question

To what extent does a difference exist in the academic achievement of mathematics students taught graph plotting using a cooperative learning strategy and those taught with the conventional method?

Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference between the academic achievement of mathematics students who were taught graph plotting using the cooperative learning strategy and those taught with the conventional method of teaching mathematics.

Materials and Methods

The study engaged the quasi-experimental descriptive survey approach to investigate the effect of cooperative learning strategy and the conventional method of teaching mathematics on students' academic achievement in graph plotting in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State Nigeria. This approach was appropriate since it allows the description of the cause-and-effect relationship between two teaching methods on how students achieve in graph plotting. The study includes senior secondary school two (SS2) students taking mathematics in the government schools of Ukwuani LGA of Delta State, Nigeria. However, 70 of these students were selected from two intact classes of 35 students each, to make up the population sample of the study, with a focus on graph plotting in the SS2 mathematics curriculum. The two intact classes comprise of an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group received instructional intervention on graph plotting using the cooperative learning strategy, while the control group received instructional intervention on graph plotting using the conventional method of teaching mathematics. The two intact classes were engaged to serve as the representative sample of the entire population under study.

The research instrument utilized for this research was the Mathematics Achievement Test on Graph Plotting (MATGP), a twenty-five (25) items multiple choice test questions on graph plotting, adapted from the West African Examination Council's past questions for Nigerian students. A reliability of 0.8 was attained for the instrument using Richard Kuderson-21, and the content validity was ascertained by a professor of Science Education in Delta State University Abraka. The MATGP was engaged to investigate the variance in students' academic achievement between the experimental and control group

after four weeks of instructional intervention. Descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, and t-test at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance, were used to measure the significant difference in students' academic achievement within the experimental group and the control group.

Ethical Consideration

In accordance with the ethical guidelines for research involving human participants, the sampled population was informed about the purpose of the study at the beginning. Participation was voluntary, and no incentives were provided. To ensure anonymity, participants were instructed not to write their names on the MATGP, except for a serial number that was assigned to differentiate the achievements between the experimental and control groups.

Results

The presentations in this section was based on the research question and null hypotheses that guided the conduct of the study.

Research Question

To what extent does a difference exist in the academic achievement of mathematics students taught graph plotting using a cooperative learning strategy and those taught with the conventional method?

Table 1. T-Test Analysis of Students' Achievement in the MATGP between Mathematics Students Who were Taught Graph Plotting Using Cooperative Learning Strategy (CLS) and those Taught with Conventional Method of Teaching Mathematics (CM)

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	T-Cal value	P-value (2TAIL)	T-Crit (2TAIL)	Decision
Experimental Group (CLS)	35	55.00	23.35	68	5.10	1.099E-06	1.98	Null Hypothesis Rejected
Control Group (CM)	35	40.93	12.70	68	5.10	1.099E-06	1.98	

Note: *significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 1 above reveals the outcomes of the t-test analysis, illustrating the differences between students' achievement in the MATGP between students who were taught graph plotting using the Cooperative Learning Strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught with the Conventional Method of teaching Mathematics (Control Group). The findings reveal a mean score of 55.00 and 40.93 in the experimental and control group respectively. The variables therefore demonstrates a difference of 14.07 in the mean scores between students achievement across the two groups. This specifies that students' achievement in the MATGP within the experimental group is slightly higher than those in the control group.

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the academic achievement of mathematics students who were taught graph plotting using the cooperative learning strategy and those taught with the conventional method of teaching mathematics.

Based on the data presented in Table 1, the t-test conducted to compare the academic achievement of students in the MATGP showed that students who were taught graph plotting using the cooperative learning strategy (experimental group), and those taught with conventional method of teaching mathematics (control group) resulted in a p-value of 1.099E-06, T-Cal. value of 5.10, and a T-Crit. value of 1.98. This reveals that at the significant value of $p \leq 0.05$, the students who was taught graph plotting with cooperative learning strategy achieved better than those taught in the conventional method of

teaching mathematics, thereby showing statistically significant difference between students achievement in the two group. The null hypothesis of the study was hereby rejected.

Discussion

The study focused on investigating the effect of cooperative learning strategy and the conventional method of teaching mathematics on students' achievement in graph plotting, within the Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The findings of the study showed that students who were taught graph plotting with cooperative learning strategy outperformed those taught with the conventional method of teaching mathematics, with a mean difference of 14.07 in student achievement. Thus, cooperative learning strategy tends to show greater effect in improving mathematics students' academic achievement in graph plotting compared to the conventional lecture method of teaching mathematics.

This result agrees with Ahmed & David (2019) who discovered that the application of cooperative learning strategy is a desirable substitute to the conventional method of teaching mathematics because two students cooperating together in learning can drive learning gains even as both learners enters the peer learning situation with low levels of aptitude. The findings of the study also agrees with Ajaja and Eravwoke (2010) who investigated the influence of cooperative learning strategy on students' performance and concluded that students usually have significantly higher achievement test scores when taught with cooperative learning strategy than in their conventional classrooms.

Conclusion

The findings of this study identifies a significant difference in students' academic achievement between students' who were taught graph plotting using the cooperative learning strategy, and those taught with the conventional method of teaching mathematics, in the Ukwuani LGA of Delta State. The study therefore upholds the existing body of knowledge which supports the application of cooperative learning strategy in secondary school science education. Further studies in this direction may look into students' preferences and readiness to cooperative learning strategy, as well as gender differences in students' mathematics achievement when utilizing the cooperative learning strategy.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declares no conflict of interest.

References

- Afzal, H., Ali, I., Aslam Khan, M., & Hamid, K. (2010). A study of university students' motivation and its relationship with their academic performance. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2899435>
- Ahmed, A., & David S. A. (2019). The input of activity based learning on students' motivation and academich achievement: a study among 12th grade science and environment students in a public school in Oman. *Science Arena Publications Special Journal of knowledge Management*, 4(4), 44-53.
- Ajaja, B., & Eravwoke, O. (2010). Effects of cooperative learning strategy on junior secondary students achievement in integrated science. *Electronic Journal of Science Education*, 14(1), 1-18.

- Altun, S. (2015). The effect of cooperative learning on students' achievement and views on science and technology courses. *International Journal of Elementary Education*, 7(3), 451-468.
- Arra, C. T., D'Antonio, M. D., & D'Antonio Jr, M. (2011). Students' Preferences for Cooperative Learning Instructional Approaches: Considerations for College Teachers. *Journal of Research in Education*, 21(1), 114-126.
- Bai, Y., Tang, B., Wang, B., Mo, D., Zhang, L., Rozelle, S., ... & Mandell, B. (2023). Impact of online computer assisted learning on education: *Experimental evidence from economically vulnerable areas of China*. *Economics of Education Review*, 94, 102-385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econedurev.2023.102385>
- Chekour, A. (2017). The effectiveness of computer-assisted math instruction in developmental classes. *AURCO Journal*, 23(Spring), 21-30.
- Chen, Y. C., Lu, Y. L., & Lien, C. J. (2021). Learning environments with different levels of technological engagement: a comparison of game-based, video-based, and traditional instruction on students' learning. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 29(8), 1363-1379. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2019.1628781>
- Ejiwale, J. (2013). Barriers to successful implementation of STEM education. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(2), 63-74.
- Foster, M. E., Anthony, J. L., Clements, D. H., Sarama, J., & Williams, J. M. (2016). Improving mathematics learning of kindergarten students through computer-assisted instruction. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 47(3), 206-232. <https://doi.org/10.5951/jresmetheduc.47.3.0206>
- Felder, R. M., & Brent, R. (2007). Cooperative learning. Active learning: *Models from the analytical sciences*, 970, 34-53.
- Iroriteraye-Adjekpovu, J. I (2022). Interactive Radio Response (IRR) Effectiveness in Small-class Size Chemistry Students Achievement. *Journal of Education, Society, and Behavioural Science*, 35(3), 32-38.
- Iroriteraye-Adjekpovu & Nwabuaku (2024). A Comparative Study on the Effectiveness of Traditional and Computer-assisted Instruction Methods in Determining Students' Achievement on Graph Plotting. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(1), 1-5. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejceel.2024.2\(1\)](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(1)).
- Khan, A., & Akhtar, M. (2017). Investigating the effectiveness of cooperative learning method on teaching of English grammar. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 39(1), 1-16.
- Lessani, A., Yunus, A., & Bakar, K. (2017). Comparison of new mathematics teaching methods with traditional method. *People: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(2), 1285-1297. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijss.2017.32.12851297>
- Nnorom, N. R. (2015). Effect of cooperative learning instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' achievement in biology in anambra state, Nigeria. *International Journal for Cross-Disciplinary Subjects in Education (IJCDSE), Special*, 5(1), 2424-2427.
- Nwabuaku, L. (2022). Understanding Curriculum Theorizing in Post-Covid Era: Fundamental Issues and Prospects in Nigeria. *Journal of the Professional Association of Curriculum Theorists and Practitioners in Nigeria*. 1(1). 51-61.
- Nwabuaku, L. (2023). Teachers' Commitment as a Predictor of Students' Academic Performance in Biology. *Delsu Journal of Educational Research and Development* 20(1), 100-108.
- Olabiyi, O. S., & Awofala, A. O. A. (2019). *Effect of co-operative learning strategy on senior secondary school students' achievement in woodwork technology*. *Acta Didactica Napocensia; Cluj-Napoca*, 12(2), 171-182. <https://doi.org/10.24193/adn.12.2.13>
- Ran, H., Kim, N. J., & Secada, W. G. (2022). A meta-analysis on the effects of technology's functions and roles on students' mathematics achievement in K-12 classrooms. *Journal of computer assisted learning*, 38(1), 258-284. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12611>

Shimazoe, J., & Aldrich, H. (2010). Group work can be gratifying: Understanding & overcoming resistance to cooperative learning. *College teaching*, 58(2), 52-57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87567550903418594>

Slavin, R. E. (1995). *Cooperative learning: theory, research and practice* (2nd ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.

Slavin, R. E. (2011). *Instruction Based on Cooperation Learning*. R. E. Meyer & P. A. Alexander (Eds), *Handbook of Research on Learning and Instruction* (pp. 344-360). New York: Taylor & Francis.

Vilardi, R. P. (2013). *Mathematics achievement: Traditional instruction and technology-assisted course delivery methods* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Alabama Libraries). Retrieved from

Wendy, J. (2005). *The implementation of cooperative learning in the classroom*. Center for Educational Studies, University of Hull, 1-2.

West African Examination Council (2012). *Chief Examiners Report WASSCE May/June*. Lagos: WAEC Press Ltd.

West Africans Examination Council (2020). *Chief Examiners Report WASSCE May/June*. Lagos WAEC Press Ltd.

West Africans Examination Council (2022). *Chief Examiners Report WASSCE May/June*. Lagos WAEC Press Ltd.

Zakaria, E., Chin, L. C., & Daud, M. Y. (2010). The effects of cooperative learning on students' mathematics achievement and attitude towards mathematics. *Journal of social sciences*, 6(2), 272-275.

